

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

REPRODUCTION OF MEDICINAL *LONICERA JAPONICA* THUNB. (CAPRIFOLIACEAE) IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE TASHKENT BOTANICAL GARDEN

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Abstract

For the first time, under the conditions of the introduction of the Tashkent Botanical Garden of Uzbekistan, the reproduction of valuable medicinal *Lonicera japonica* Thunb. was studied. Thus, the optimal temperature for the germination of *Lonicera japonica* seeds in laboratory conditions is +20 +22 °C, at which the germination rate was 58%. It was noted that under greenhouse conditions, 93% of cuttings, when treated with the Kornevin stimulant, formed roots at an air temperature of 20-22 °C and a relative air humidity of 49-53%. It was established that in open ground conditions, 85% of cuttings treated with the Kornevin stimulant developed roots at an air temperature of 25-27 °C and a relative air humidity of 49-52%. Considering the effectiveness of vegetative propagation of the species *Lonicera japonica*, it is possible to supply the necessary raw materials for the pharmaceutical industry in the future. It is noted that the studied medicinal species has adapted well to the conditions of introduction. This species is also recommended for improving the aesthetic condition and landscaping of cities, and landscape design.

Keywords: *Lonicera japonica*, bush shoots, callus, seed germination, Kornevin stimulant, root, vegetative propagation.

Caprifoliaceae Vent. there are about 500 species of its family on Earth, belonging to 15 genus, which are leaf-shedding, evergreen, sometimes creeping, in rare cases, low-lying trees or herbaceous plants. They are distributed mainly in the Northern Hemisphere, temperate and subtropical regions. Most species of this family are extremely ornamental and medicinal forest plants. One of the large genera of the Caprifoliaceae family is *Lonicera* L. it includes about 200 species worldwide. The distribution range of this genus species is quite wide. It is distributed from the Caucasus to Siberia or Altai to the Himalayan mountains from the western regions of Japan, Korea, China. 10 species of this genus are found in the flora of Uzbekistan [1]. There are not only decorative species, but also edible ones. The berries of the plant are quite suitable for food and have many useful properties. The shrubs are frost-resistant, unpretentious in care and differ in early ripeness. Types of honeysuckle are useful for the human body, due to its chemical composition. Berries contain a lot of vitamins, trace elements and nutrients: vitamin B, C, P, carotene, also the composition of honeysuckle includes chemical elements such as copper, manganese, boron, iodine, silicon. Among other things, fruits contain a number of bioactive additives. These include: pectins, tannins, anthocyanins, sugars, organic acids. Species of the genus *Lonicera* is rich in various substances that provide invaluable benefits for the body. That is why it is widely used in folk medicine.

Fruits are also used to relieve inflammation affecting the mucous membrane of the throat, oral cavity. The leaves are used to prepare a tincture, which is used to rub the eyes affected by conjunctivitis. Species of *Lonicera* are also rich in vitamins, which allow it to cope

perfectly with reduced immunity. Folk healers recommend using berries in autumn and spring during colds and for the purpose of treating acute respiratory infections. Branches, leaves, and the bark of a shrub have useful properties. Species of *Lonicera* are useful for pancreatitis, gastritis, liver diseases, as it has an antioxidant effect and allows you to remove harmful substances that have a negative effect on the organ. The substances included in the fruit are involved in the work of the kidneys and urinary system.

Lonicera japonica seeds were brought and sown to the Tashkent Botanical Garden Academician F.N. Rusanov in 1947 (Fig. 1).

According to the description of Wagner et al. [2], *Lonicera japonica* is sprawling and twining lianas; young stems pubescent; leaves ovate, elliptic, oblong or broadly lanceolate, blades 3-8 cm long, 1-3.5 cm wide, pubescent, becoming glabrate above, entire or young lower leaves sometimes lobed; flowers 2 in axillary cymes, bracts 1-2 cm long, bracteoles suborbicular, ca. 1 mm long; corolla white, turning yellowish or tinged pink, 2-lipped, 2-3 cm long; berries bluish black, globose, 6-7 mm in diameter. The flowering duration of individual plant is usually 5-8 days, but the flowering period is from May to September in the field, can be divided into six stages, i.e. the juvenile bud stage, the third green stage, the second white stage, the complete white stage, the silver flowering stage and the gold flowering stage. *Lonicera japonica* often grows in hillside scrub, rocks pile and roadside, and the highest altitude is 1500 m. Due to its beautiful flowers and strong roots, *Lonicera japonica* was cultivated for people to watch, conserve water and soil in world [3].

Figure 1 – *Lonicera japonica* in the growing conditions of the Tashkent Botanical Garden

Determination of laboratory germination of the seeds of *Lonicera japonica*

Earlier, also under the conditions of the introduction of the Tashkent Botanical Garden by Temirov and Rakhimova [4], similar studies were conducted on the bioecological features of some decorative species and forms (*Chamaecyparis lawsoniana* (Murr.) Parl., *J. communis* L., *J. oblonga* M. B., *J. squamata* Lamb. and 5 decorative forms: *Platyclusus (Biota) orientalis* f. *compacta* Unger f. *Beissn.*, *B. orientalis* f. *aurea* (Dauvesse) Hornibr., *Thuja occidentalis* f. *columna* Spaeth., *T. occidentalis* f. *smaragd* Beissn., *T. occidentalis* f. *aurea spicata* Beissn.) of the Cupressaceae family, widely used in landscaping and landscape design. For the first time, the possibility of vegetative reproduction in open ground with rooting rate of cuttings up to 95% has been shown.

To determine the germination of seeds in laboratory conditions, the germination of 50 seeds of a plant was studied on filter paper moistened with distilled water in a Petri dish when exposed to 3 different temperatures.

For vegetative propagation of *Lonicera japonica* according to the method of Ivanova [5], Hartman & Kester [6] cuttings were prepared from annual branches. For green cuttings of woody plants Kornevin

is usually used 50-200 mg/l; and indolylbutyric acid (IMA) – at concentrations of 25-100 mg/l.

For vegetative propagation of *Lonicera japonica*, cuttings were harvested in early spring before the start of plant vegetation and taken from the middle part of the shoots. This, of course, is of great importance in the high percentage of rooting cuttings. The cuttings were made 10-12 cm long, depending on the distance between the shoots on the branches. The cuttings were laid for 12-14 hours, 100 pieces each, in two versions: with the use of the Kornevin stimulant and in the control (plain water) versions (03.03.2022). For rooting cuttings in the conditions of the greenhouse complex, special areas 1.2x1 m long were prepared, on which river sand 8–10 cm thick was poured. The planting depth of the cuttings was 4–6 cm, the distance between rows was 5x7 cm. pouring water with a watering can. The average temperature in the greenhouse was 20-22 °C.

To determine the germination of seeds in laboratory conditions, they were grown and examined 3 times at temperatures of +20 +22 °C, +24 +26 °C and +28 +30 °C. The optimal temperature for seed germination in laboratory conditions was +20 +22 °C, at which germination was 58%, at +24+26 °C - 35%, and at +28+30 °C – 8% (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Laboratory germination of the seeds of *Lonicera japonica* (in percentages)

It was noted that *L. japonica* cuttings treated with the Kornevin stimulant in greenhouse conditions formed a callus after 9 days (03/12/2022). After 17 days (03/25/2022), it was found that the primary roots were formed. During this time, it was noticed that buds and new leaves formed in the upper part of the cuttings, and 93% of the cuttings formed roots.

In the heteroauxin and control variants, the callus formed on days 12-13, primary roots - on days 25-27, root germination was noted in 88% of the cuttings.

In order to determine the qualitative indicators of the effectiveness of vegetative propagation of *L. japonica* in open ground conditions, it was treated in three different ways: root – indolebutyric acid (IBA), heteroauxin – indoleacetic acid (IAA), control – ordinary water treated for 10-12 hours with stimulants. The planting depth of the cuttings is 4-6 cm, the distance between the rows is 5x7 cm. Watering was carried out regularly with a watering can to keep the humidity of the sand at the same level. It was noted that *L. japonica* cuttings treated with the Kornevin stimulant in open ground conditions formed a callus after 15 days (03/18/2022). At this time, it was noted that the air temperature is 18-20 °C, and the relative humidity is 54-56%. It was established that the primary roots were formed after 32 days (04/04/2022) in cuttings using the Kornevin stimulant. It was found that in 85% of the cuttings the roots were formed at an air temperature of 25-27 °C and a relative air humidity of 49-52%.

It was noted that cuttings of this species, treated with Heteroauxin, and control variants formed callus after 16 days (March 19, 2022) at an air temperature of 18-20 °C and a relative air humidity of 54-56%. In the course of our observations, it was noted that the root formed after 38-40 days (04.10.2022) (Fig. 4). The rooting rate of cuttings in heteroauxin is 78-80%. During vegetative propagation of the studied introducers, it was noted that the early formation of primary roots and the percentage of germination of cuttings were higher (85-93%) in the Kornevin stimulant than in the heteroauxin and control variant.

When observing cuttings for vegetative propagation, in the first ten days of June, it was found that the length of the main root of *L. japonica* is 28-30 cm, with the third-order roots being most formed. It was noted that the length of the stem reached 34.5 cm, and the secondary branches grew to 14-15 cm.

In Kornevin's stimulator, the length of the root of *L. japonica* is 117-118 cm, the length of the cutting is 10-12 cm, the length of the first branch is 129-131 cm, the length of the second branch is 109-110 cm, the third is 54-56 cm, and the number of secondary branches is 4, 37-59 cm. The length of the root of *L. japonica* treated with the stimulant heteroauxin is 61-63 cm, the length of the trunk is 10-12 cm, the length of the first branch is 110-112 cm, the length of the second branch is 95 cm -97 cm, the third is 41-42 cm, and the number of shoots of the second order is 4, with a length of 33-50 cm.

Lonicera japonica, a widely used traditional Chinese medicine, was taken to treat the exopathogenic wind-heat, epidemic febrile diseases, sores, carbuncles

and some infectious diseases. At the same time, *Lonicera japonica* could be used as healthy food, cosmetics, ornamental groundcover, and so on. Dry leaves and flowers (*Flos Lonicerae Japonicae*) are used in traditional Chinese medicine to treat fever, headache associated with colds, cough, thirst, and certain inflammations including sore throat, skin infections, and tumor necrosis. *Lonicera japonica* has been used for thousands of years in China. Now, more than 140 chemical compounds have been isolated; and studies show *Lonicera japonica* possesses wide pharmacological actions. Meanwhile, it could be used as healthy food, ornamental groundcover, etc. [7].

Phenolic contents, antioxidant and tyrosinase inhibitory activities of *Lonicera japonica* was studied by Dung et al. [8]. The study of the effect of carbohydrate type on the morphogenetic potential of *Lonicera caerulea* L. in vitro was conducted by Orlova et al. [9, 10].

Application of introduced representatives of *Lonicera pileata* Oliv. in landscaping of the right-bank forest-steppe of Ukraine was carried out by Varlachenko et al. [11]. Progress in research on pesticide residues of *Lonicera japonica* Flos was investigated by Lu et al. [12]. Target sequence capture data shed light on the deeper evolutionary relationship on the subgenus *Chamaecerasus* of *Lonicera* (Caprifoliaceae) studied by Sun et al. [13].

A taxonomic study on pollen morphology characteristics, chromosome karyotype characteristics, floral and fruit pigment compositions of 13 species and hybrids of *Lonicera* L., is given by Dalong et al. [14]. Bioactive constituents from the leaves of *Lonicera japonica* studied by Yu et al. [15].

In Uzbekistan, research on the growth and development, seed germination and vegetative reproduction of the valuable medicinal plant *Lonicera japonica*, introduced into the Tashkent Botanical Garden, is carried out by us for the first time. Similar studies have not been carried out in Uzbekistan so far.

Thus, the optimum temperature for the germination of *Lonicera japonica* seeds in laboratory conditions is +20 +22 °C, at which the germination rate was 58%. It was noted that under greenhouse conditions, 93% of the cuttings, when treated with Kornevin's stimulant, formed roots at an air temperature of 20-22 °C and a relative air humidity of 49-53%. It has been established that in open ground conditions, 85% of the cuttings treated with Kornevin's stimulant developed roots at an air temperature of 25-27 °C and a relative air humidity of 49-52%.

Today, in world practice, people's need for medicinal preparations made from plants is increasing, and medicinal plants are widely used in medicine. Biologically active substances and extracts obtained from plants are very popular in developed countries such as Japan, France, Germany, Italy. Herbal medicines are important in many developing countries in Asia. Taking into account the effectiveness of vegetative propagation of *Lonicera japonica* species, it is possible to supply the necessary raw materials for the pharmaceutical industry in the future.

It was noted that this valuable medicinal species adapted well to the conditions of the introduction of the

Tashkent Botanical Garden, quickly recovered and continued the resumption of vegetation even when the plant was affected by cold weather, did not lose its decorative properties. This type is also recommended for improving the aesthetic state of the cities of our Republic and for enriching the range of trends in landscaping and landscape design.

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